

Examination of the Unsaturated Acids in Fish Oil.

Part I. Oil of *Labeo Rohita*.

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While engaged in investigating the possibilities of deodourising fish oils without having recourse to the well-known process of hydrogenation, the authors had occasion to refer to the literature on the nature of the unsaturated acids likely to be present and were surprised to find that there were no data available as to the nature of acids in tropical fish oils with which they were working while the acids present in some fish oils of colder climates were only imperfectly known. Efforts were therefore directed to the examination of the unsaturated acids occurring in the stomach-oil of *Labeo Rohita* (the "ruhu" of Indian rivers), which is extensively used for edible purposes.

This lack of information regarding the chemical nature of fish oils is no doubt due to the great experimental difficulties attending the investigation of marine oils. Owing to the unsaturation of the fatty acids and the consequent possibilities of a large number of isomerides as well as the complexity of the mixture of fatty acids of similar nature occurring in fish oils, the difficulty of experimental investigation is greatly multiplied.¹

Hofstaedter (*Annalen*, 1854, 91, 177) was the first to point out the presence of unsaturated acids in marine oils. The most notable workers in recent years are Fahrion, (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1893, 17, 521, 684), Bull (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3570), Tolman (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1909, 1, 341), Twitchell (*ibid*, 1914, 6, 564; 1917, 9, 581), Tsujimoto (*J. Coll. Eng. Imp. Uni. Tokyo*, 1906, 4, 1; *J. Chem. Ind. Japan*, 1926, 23, 1007), Brown and Beal (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 1289), Armstrong and Hilditch (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 180T) and Hilditch and Lovern (*ibid*, 1928, 47, 105T) who investigated the following marine oils:—cod-liver, menhaden, sardine,

¹ The difficulties of isolating the unsaturated acids in the pure state may be appreciated from the fact that even a simple unsaturated acid such as oleic acid, has been obtained in pure condition only recently (Holde and Gorges, *Z. angew. Chem.*, 1926, 39, 1448).

herring, salmon, and lofoten oils—all obtained from colder climates. It has been found by these authors that chemically these marine oils are similar amongst themselves but quite different from vegetable and animal oils, and contain highly unsaturated acids of high molecular weight containing fourteen to twenty-two atoms of carbon and a maximum of six double bonds in the molecule. Tsujimoto (*loc. cit.*) found an acid of C_{18} -series with four double bonds as an invariable constituent of all fish oils. This acid, named clupanodonic acid, was according to him, responsible for fishy odour. Later however, he found that the acid was really one of C_{22} -series with five double bonds, and transferred the name clupanodonic acid to this compound to indicate the invariable constituent of all fish oils. Some workers have, however, retained the name for the original C_{18} -acid, with the result that a great confusion prevails as to nomenclature. It is interesting to note that in the oil under investigation, the authors could not detect either the C_{18} - or C_{22} -acid.

The fish oil under investigation was extracted in the laboratory from fresh samples and was found to be free from any nitrogenous matter. It was light yellow in colour, and when preserved in well-stoppered bottles, did not turn rancid for months; though on exposure to air it turned reddish and developed a more objectionable odour. On standing, a solid matter, the so-called fish stearin, separated out. This fish stearin is evidently less unsaturated than the liquid oil, the iodine value of the former being 121.4 (Wijs) and of the latter 187.35, while that of the average oil is 130.6. The usual constants of the oil are given below:—

Specific gravity at 15°	...	0.9230.
Refractive index	...	1.4622 at 29°.
Optical activity	...	Nil.
Saponification value	...	191.4
Acid value	...	1.116
Hehner value	...	91.1
Reichert-Messel value	...	0.668
Unsaponifiable matter	...	0.84%
Acetyl value	...	Nil.
Iodine value (Wijs)		
Oil from smaller fish	...	61.65
" " bigger "	...	118.65
" " biggest "	...	180.80
Glycerol	...	10.2%
Loss of volatile matter at 200°, for 2 hrs.	...	1.68%

It will be observed that the iodine value of the oil changes to an enormous extent according to the state of development of the fish, the older and bigger fish yielding oils of higher iodine value. This has also been observed by other investigators in the case of linseed oil—the oil from the ripe seed being more unsaturated than those from the raw. The nature of fish oils is also dependent on climatic conditions—those from colder climates being less saturated than tropical oils (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 182T).

The oil from the largest fish having I. V._x (iodine value) 190.6 was used for the purpose of this investigation. The mixed fatty acids obtained from this oil by usual methods had the following characteristics.

Melting point	..	39°
Titer (solidifying point)	..	29°
Iodine value	..	149.6
Mean M.W.	...	295.3

The mixed acids had the characteristic odour of fish oil. They were separated into solid and liquid acids for the purpose of examination.

Of the different methods of separating saturated from unsaturated acids, the authors have found the lead-salt-alcohol method of Twitchell (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 806) the best.¹ While Varrentrapp's lead-salt-ether method gave 38.4% of solid acids, (I.V. 16.3) and 61.6 % of liquid acids (I.V. 170.8), Twitchell's method gave 28.1% of solid acids (I.V. 2.4), and 71.9 % of liquid acids (I.V. 180.8). The liquid acids separated by either method had, unlike the solid acids, the characteristic fishy odour. The liquid acids obtained by Twitchell's process were however, more viscous, due apparently to the absence of any solid acids dissolved in it. This is also in agreement with the high iodine value.

As both the methods of Varrentrapp and Twitchell are extremely laborious and require large amounts of solvents, the authors

¹ No satisfactory separation was possible by barium-soap-benzene method of Farnsteiner (*Z. Nahr. Genussm.*, 1898, (2) 1, 390) which was used by Brown and Beal in their study of fish oils, part of the solid and oleic acids coming over in the liquid fraction. The recent method of Bertram (*Z. Unters. Lebensmittel*, 1927, 84, 481), though said to be satisfactory in the case of solid acids is however inapplicable for the separation of liquid acids.

subsequently had recourse to the method of Tortelli and Ruggeri (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology of Oils, Fats and Waxes," 6th Ed., Vol. I, p. 560) which was found to be very suitable to handle large amounts of acid mixtures, though the process could not be used for quantitative purpose. Having separated the unsaturated acids, the authors next proceeded to isolate and identify the various individual acids and to estimate them wherever possible.

Attempts to isolate oleic or any other unsaturated acids by the fractional crystallization of lithium salts (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1928, 47, 30T.) from acetone, or alcohol of different strengths, proved unsuccessful. The acid isolated by this process from the alcohol insoluble lithium salts had I.V., 128.5 and a mean mol. wt. 271.5. This is evidently a mixture of oleic acid with more unsaturated acids of lower molecular weight, perhaps with hexadecatrienoic acid, $C_{16}H_{26}O_2$ found later in these investigations. Attempts to separate the individual acids by fractional distillation of methyl esters in vacuum (5 mm.) were found to be unsatisfactory.

Better results have been obtained by the bromination method. The liquid acids obtained by Tortelli and Ruggeri method (*loc. cit.*) were brominated (1) in 3% ethereal solution in presence of 2 c.c. of glacial acetic acid per gm. of liquid acid at 5° (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology of Oils Fats and Waxes" Vol. I, p. 581): and (2) in 10% dry ethereal solution at -10° without the addition of acetic acid (Eibner and Muggenthaler, *Farben-Zeitung*, 1912, No. 3 ff.). The yield of ether insoluble polybromides by the former method was 23.8% (blackening point 238°-39°) and by the latter method 31.45% (blackening point 237°-38°). Bromination by the latter method is therefore more complete and is in agreement with the observation of Eibner and Muggenthaler, that the more glacial acetic acid used, the lower the yield of hexabromide.

The bromides of the unsaturated fatty acids thus obtained in two fractions (ether soluble and ether insoluble). were examined separately. The ether-insoluble fraction obtained by the second process was an amorphous milky white substance, which became brown on drying at 100°. It had 65.5% bromine.

The usual method of separating the higher polybromides (*e.g.*, of clupanodonic acid) from the lower hexabromides is fractional treatment with benzene. (Lewkowitsch, "Chemical Technology of Oils, Fats and Waxes, Vol. I, p. 584). But in this case a separation by

this method was not possible as both higher and lower bromides were partly soluble in boiling benzene. The desired separation was however effected by chloroform. By repeated treatment of the polybromides with chloroform in the cold, a residue (A) was obtained in sufficiently pure state (blackening point 242°), while the chloroform soluble portion, after distilling off the solvent was again separated into two fractions by treatment with benzene in the cold. The portion insoluble in the cold benzene (B), and purified by treatment with boiling benzene, melted at 171° and was identified as the hexabromide of linolenic acid, while the portion soluble in benzene (C), was found on analysis to have the formula, $C_{17}H_{28}O_2Br_6$ (hexabromide of hexadecatrienoic acid).

Tetrosapentenoic Acid, $C_{24}H_{38}O_2$.—The chloroform insoluble residue (A) was found on analysis to agree with the formula $C_{24}H_{38}O_2Br_{10}$ indicating the existence of an acid of C_{24} -series with five double bonds. (Found: Br, 69.055; C, 24.76; H, 3.37. $C_{24}H_{38}O_2Br_{10}$ requires Br, 69.1; C, 24.87; H, 3.28 per cent.). The only experimental evidence of this acid is found in the work of Carter (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, **47**, 31T) who found it in mutton-bird oil and identified it through the bromo-compound. From a reference to the original work of Carter it cannot be discovered, how this highly complex bromide, mixed perhaps with other polybromides of highly unsaturated acids, was purified. It is however significant that he found the blackening point of the polybromide to be 200° , while that of our product was 242° (sharp). This is perhaps due to the care with which we purified our bromo-compound with the help of chloroform. It will be observed that the blackening point of octabromostearic acid, $C_{18}H_{28}O_2Br_8$ is 200° , and that the blackening point increases with increase in the number of carbon atoms and in bromine content of the molecule (Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.*, p. 580). The low blackening point found by Carter may be due either to impurities or to an acid isomeric with our product. Carter has not given any name to this acid. Following the usual scientific nomenclature, the authors prefer to call this 'tetrosapentenoic acid,' to indicate twenty-four atoms of carbon with five double bonds, in the molecule.

Linolenic Acid, $C_{18}H_{30}O_2$.—Another highly unsaturated acid, $C_{18}H_{30}O_2$, has been found in the mixture of liquid acids. The hexabromide of linolenic acid is generally soluble in benzene. But the hexabromide of linolenic acid as obtained from this fish oil is

evidently insoluble in cold benzene, for the authors have been able to separate the chloroform soluble bromide into two fractions one of which is insoluble in benzene as already stated. The benzene insoluble fraction carefully purified with boiling benzene had m.p. 171° (sharp). The analytical data are in close agreement with formula, $C_{18}H_{30}O_2Br_6$. (Found Br, 63.36; C, 28.38; H, 4.00 $C_{18}H_{30}O_2Br_6$ requires Br, 63.32; C, 28.49; H, 3.95 per cent.). The melting point of hexabromide of linolenic acid ranges from 185° to 135° , the usual value being 180° (Lewkowitsch, *loc. cit.* p. 584). The difference in m.p. of our product may be accounted for by the large number of possible isomerides of linolenic acid.

It is note-worthy that a considerable amount of hexabromide (m.p. 171°) was isolated from the ether soluble bromides as alcohol insoluble compound. The hexabromide of linolenic acid is apparently soluble in ether, or in the liquid bromides to some extent. On examination of the liquid bromides, the bromine content was found to be too high for dibromostearic acid, apparently due to the solubility of higher bromides. After several unsuccessful attempts to separate the higher bromides from the mixture of liquid bromides (ether soluble), the authors at last found in alcohol a suitable solvent for the lower bromides, a solid hexabromide remaining behind as an insoluble compound. It was purified by recrystallising from alcohol. On analysis this was found to be the hexabromide of linolenic acid, identical with that obtained from the ether insoluble fraction (m.p. 171° , Br., 63.4 per cent.).

Hexadecatrienoic Acid, $C_{16}H_{26}O_2$.—This acid has been definitely identified by the authors in the benzene-soluble fraction (C) obtained from solid polybromides. It melted at 158° , after recrystallisation from benzene. (Found: Br, 65.58; C, 26.11; H, 3.80. $C_{16}H_{26}O_2Br_6$ requires Br, 65.75; C, 26.30; H, 3.56 per cent.). A mention of the name of this acid is made by Brown and Beal (*loc. cit.*), who surmised the probable existence of this acid in menhaden oil. The acid in question or any of its derivatives have not been isolated. It is merely surmised that the fraction may be a mixture of 2 parts of clupanodonic acid and one part of hexadecatrienoic acid. It is however obvious that the I. V. and mean mol. wt. of the fraction may be due to the combination of other acids as well. The presence of the hexadecatrienoic acid in the oil of *Labeo rohita* has been proved by the authors by isolation of the pure bromide and its complete analysis.

The scheme of analysis of the solid polybromides as adopted by the authors is shown graphically as follows:

Linolic Acid, $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$.—When the ether-soluble bromides, after complete removal of ether, were treated with low-boiling petroleum ether in the usual manner, no separation of any tetrabromide took place, nothing going in solution in boiling petrol. This fact indicates that linolic acid $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$ is not present in any appreciable quantity in the oil under investigation. This conclusion is further supported by the results obtained by the careful oxidation of the

liquid fatty acids with alkaline potassium permanganate in the cold, no tetrahydroxystearic acid (sativic acid) being obtained.

Liquid Bromides.—The filtrate obtained after removal of the insoluble polybromides, consisting of ether-soluble bromides, was washed with aqueous sodium thiosulphate to remove the excess of bromine. A portion of the ether was distilled off and the rest kept overnight. A precipitate, m. p. 168°, was obtained, and on examination was found to be hexabromostearic acid (obtained from linolenic acid). All the higher solid bromides could not, however, be separated with the help of ether. This could be effected by the addition of absolute alcohol when a solid bromide separated (12.5 per cent. of the liquid fatty acids), which as already mentioned was found to be hexabromostearic acid. The liquid bromides obtained from the alcoholic solution is a thick brown syrupy liquid (yield, 145.1 per cent. of the total unsaturated fatty acids, corresponding to 84.0 per cent. bromine free liquid fatty acids). Its bromine content (44.24 per cent.) is too high for dibromostearic acid (obtained from oleic acid). Further separation of the liquid bromides by means of solvents proved unsuccessful. On debrominating the liquid bromides and on brominating them again a very small yield of ether insoluble polybromides was obtained. This blackened at 237°-238°, possessed properties quite similar to the ether insoluble polybromides previously obtained from unsaturated acids and proved to be a mixture of different polybromides.

This shows that a part of the highly unsaturated acids escaped complete bromination and in this form was found in the ether soluble liquid bromides, thus increasing the bromine content of the liquid bromides of less unsaturated acids. This fact makes the quantitative figures of the different acids as stated subsequently only approximate ones those present in the liquid bromides having escaped estimation.

Oxidation of the Liquid Fatty Acids.—The liquid fatty acids obtained by Tortelli and Ruggeri's method were neutralised with potassium hydroxide and oxidised with alkaline potassium permanganate solution (1.5 per cent.) at 28°. The yield of hydroxy-acids obtained by this method was however very poor, and the accompanying unoxidised fatty acids could not be completely removed even by repeated washing with petrol, in which the hydroxy-acids are insoluble. The hydroxy-acids could not thus be obtained in a pure form for analysis.

The mother-liquor (from the permanganate oxidation) obtained after removal of the insoluble hydroxy-acids, was examined for the hydroxy-acids from higher unsaturated acids, (e.g., sativic and linusic acids) but no trace of either could be found. Evidently the higher unsaturated acids were broken down during oxidation.

In order to make the process of oxidation less drastic the liquid fatty acids were next oxidised with a mere dilute solution of potassium permanganate (0.75 per cent.) at 0° (Holde, " Hydrocarbon Oils and Saponifiable Fats and Waxes, 2nd. English Ed., p. 375). The procedure is represented graphically below.

Fraction (A) was recrystallised twice from 95 per cent. alcohol when a milky white stuff was obtained, m. p. 116°-116.5°. The analytical data agree with those for dihydroxyasellinic acid $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_4$. (Found: Neutralisation value, 185.1; C, 67.17; H, 11.11. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_4$ requires neutralisation value, 185.6; C, 67.48; H, 11.38 per cent.) This compound confirms the presence of "asellinic acid" (Fabrions' acid) $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$ in the liquid fatty acids.

The above named acid was discovered by Fabrion (*Chem. Review*, 1926, 3, 425) in cod-liver oil; the existence of this acid which has an odd number carbon atoms has been doubted by many investigators, notably by Lewkowitsch (*loc. cit.*, Vol. 1, p. 115). Fabrion has however, maintained the existence of this acid in fish oil in a subsequent contribution (*Chem. Umschu.*, 1927, 24, 6). In view of these contradictory opinions the authors made special efforts to obtain it in the purest possible state and the results confirm Fabrion's observations,

Fraction (B) was also recrystallised several times from 95 per cent. alcohol and was found to melt finally at $125^{\circ}\text{--}26^{\circ}$. The following analytical data identify it as dihydroxystearic acid. (Found: neutralisation value, 176.9; C, 87.87; H, 11.88. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_4$ requires neutralisation value 177.5; C, 88.81; H, 11.47 per cent.) The presence of oleic acid in fish oil is thus confirmed.

The usual m. p. of dihydroxystearic acid is stated to be 137° . Other melting points ranging from $137^{\circ}\text{--}119^{\circ}$ (Lewkowitsch. *loc. cit.*, Vol. I, 238.) are also found in literature. The m. p. of the dihydroxystearic acid obtained from whale oil by Armstrong and Hilditch (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 182T) is $124^{\circ}\text{--}25^{\circ}$ which is in close agreement with ours.

Approximate Estimation of the Unsaturated Acids.

Estimation of Tetrapentenoic acid, $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$ 100 G. of liquid fatty acids gave 31.45 g. of ether-insoluble bromides (Br, 55.5 per cent.). Thus 10.75 per cent. of the liquid acids gave the ether-insoluble bromides. The bromine contents of chloroform soluble and insoluble fractions were 64.92 per cent. and 69.05 per cent. respectively whence the p. c. of chloroform-insoluble bromide (in the ether insoluble bromides) was 13.8. Thus of 31.45 g. of insoluble bromide only 13.8 per cent. was $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2\text{Br}_{10}$, which was obtainable from 1.34 g. of liquid fatty acids. Hence, the p. c. of $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$ in the liquid fatty acids = 1.34.

Estimation of Linolenic acid $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2$ and Hexadecatrienoic acids $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2$ in ether insoluble bromides.

9.41 G. gave chloroform soluble bromides, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{Br}_6$ and $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2\text{Br}_6$, whose bromine contents were 63.32 per cent. and 65.75 per cent. respectively, while that of the mixture was 64.94 per cent. Thus, 66.66 per cent. of the chloroform soluble bromides was $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2\text{Br}_6$. Hence, of 9.41 g. of liquid acids, 6.13 g. gave benzene-soluble bromide,—i.e., $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_2\text{Br}_6$ and 3.28 g. benzene insoluble bromide—i.e. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2\text{Br}_6$.

Thus, the p. c. of linolenic acid = 3.28, and that of hexadecatrienoic acid = 6.13.

Estimation of linolenic acid, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_2$ in ether-soluble bromides.—100 G. of liquid fatty acids gave 12.5 p. c. of ether soluble bromide (Br, 63.32 per cent.). Hence 12.5 g. of bromide were obtained from 4.58 g. of liquid fatty acids. The p. c. of linolenic acid = 4.58.

To sum up :

1. Tetrapentenoic acid, $C_{24}H_{38}O_2 = 1.84$ per cent.
 2. Linolenic acid, $C_{18}H_{30}O_2$.
 - (a) In ether insoluble bromides = 9.28 per cent.
 - (b) In ether soluble bromides = 4.58 per cent.
 3. Hexadecatrienoic acid, $C_{16}H_{26}O_2 = 6.18$ per cent.
 4. Oleic, asellinic and other acids giving
liquid bromides = 84.0 per cent.
- Total 99.83 per cent.

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